

ACTIONS FOR CO-GOVERNANCE

Background

This work is part of the H2020 project JUSTNature Task 7.2 “Assess, recommend and monitor co-governance”. To provide cities with inspiration and practical examples of co-governance in action, we identified the following key topics and developed a fact sheet for each of them:

- Expanding access to green space
- Building capacity
- Activating the space
- Changing management responsibilities

For each topic, we researched relevant examples from practice to inform the development of the fact sheets.

Each fact sheet includes...

- A list of possible actions, each with a practice example with links to further reading and the phase(s) it relates to. We focused on actions relevant for the implementation and operation phases, as these are often the most challenging stages for operationalising co-governance.
- A list of indicators that are relevant for monitoring progress in those activities.
- A ‘deeper dive’ into one action – i.e. one practice example with more detailed information on how it was done.

We’ve included links to selected practice examples in the action sheets that we think are particularly interesting. If you want to find more case studies related to governance of NbS, you might try one of these searchable online databases:

- Urban Governance Atlas: <https://interlace-hub.com/urban-governance-atlas>
- Network Nature case-study finder: <https://networknature.eu/network-nature-case-study-finder>

TOPIC: Expanding access to green space

What it means for co-governance

Spending time in nature is of great value for mental health and wellbeing, but **not all urban residents enjoy easy access** to natural spaces, especially in cities where population growth is high and land under increasing pressure. One way to **unlock more** open green space for urban communities is through converting an existing space to a new use or expanding access rights, whether through making a private green space publicly accessible or converting a car park to a green space. To successfully initiate such changes means first **engaging** with those currently with a 'right' to the space (whether legal or perceived), e.g. a private owner, local traders or residents who normally park cars in the street. Such changes also affect the governance of that space, because the **associated rights and responsibilities for using it also change**, which can create potential for a new collaboration. A **new set of rules** and management procedures is likely needed to make sure different needs and uses are accommodated, without impacting negatively on one another.

Expanding access to green space can improve distributional justice because more people can enjoy the benefits of nature. It can improve recognitional justice, if **people with a particular need for certain benefits are actively helped** to access the space (also see Fact sheet: Activating the space). It can also improve procedural justice, if **opportunities** are provided to participate in **decisions** related to use of the space, to **managing** the space and **caring** for the vegetation (also see Fact sheet: Building Capacity and Fact sheet: Changing management responsibilities).

Recommended indicators

- #4 Participation: Degree of participation
- #8 Ensuring equitable access to NbS
- #11 Existence of designated municipal program manager who supports a specific neighbourhood in different areas
- #17 Valuing diversity and inclusion
- #18 Collaborative arrangements
- #31 Broad consensus and understanding for shared vision
- #38 Empowering through co-creation process
- #40 Inclusion of direct day-to-day-management of green spaces in the (planning) process
- #53 Attention for local conditions
- #55 Identification and involvement of diverse and vulnerable group of key actors representing different sectors
- #62 Representativeness of participants

Recommended action	Practice example
<p>Open up a private or semi-public space to selected users for a fixed time period (e.g. during summer, or after hours)</p> <p>Phase: Operation</p>	<p>Name: Spielhöfe (play courtyards)</p> <p>City: Nürnberg</p> <p>Year: Since 1992</p> <p>What: For over 60 years, the City of Nuremberg has been making its school courtyards available as playgrounds for kids and teenagers outside of school hours (between 1-9pm during April to October and 1-6pm during November to March), and since 1992 has begun to refurbish them for this purpose. In that time, at least 46 school courtyards (roughly 50% of all school courtyards) have been turned into 'play courtyards'. For more details, see Deeper Dive below.</p> <p>Link: https://playground-landscape.com/de/article/1023-spielhoeefe-schulhoeefe-als-oeffentliche-spielplaetze.html.</p>
<p>Make a street temporarily car-free</p> <p>Phase: Operation</p>	<p>Name: Living Streets</p> <p>City: Ghent</p> <p>Year: 2012</p> <p>What: Living Streets, Belgium, has evolved from an experimental pilot project in Ghent into a long term programme to temporarily convert streets into car-free zones in Ghent and other Belgian cities. The City supervises the entire process, ensures the necessary permits and provides signage and street furniture. Local residents are responsible for maintenance and events.</p> <p>Link: https://citychangers.org/the-streets-are-alive-in-ghent/</p>
<p>Open up a private space to selected users</p> <p>Phase: Operation</p>	<p>Name: Skyfarm</p> <p>City: Melbourne</p> <p>Year: 2021</p> <p>What: The company Biofilta converted a bare rooftop to an urban farm. The company negotiated an 8 year lease from the building owner, and capital works were partly funded by the City of Melbourne's Urban Forest Fund Melbourne, which matches private funding for greening projects where both environmental and social benefits can be demonstrated by applicants. Access to the rooftop is restricted, with visits available for a fee. However, the Skyfarm offers social benefits through partnering with local food distribution charity OzHarvest.</p> <p>Link: https://www.melbourne.vic.gov.au/community/greening-the-city/urban-forest-fund/funded-projects/pages/melbourne-skyfarm.aspx</p>
<p>Open up space to all potential users for a temporary period</p> <p>Phase: Operation</p>	<p>Name: Stalled Spaces</p> <p>City: Glasgow</p> <p>Year: Since 2011</p> <p>What: Since 2011, Glasgow's Stalled Spaces programme, a partnership between the city administration and the Glasgow Housing Association, has created temporary community uses on over 100 vacant or under-utilised sites. Successful projects have relied on leadership from community members, a legal agreement between parties, and links to other local initiatives.</p> <p>Link: https://www.glasgow.gov.uk/index.aspx?articleid=17878</p>

Deeper dive: Play courtyards in Nuremberg

City: Nuremberg

Year: Since 1992

Figure: Redesigned play courtyard at St Leonhard's high school: before and after.
Credit: Carlo Niklas, SÖR, Stadt Nürnberg.

For over 60 years, the City of Nuremberg has been making its school courtyards available as playgrounds for kids and teenagers outside of school hours (between 1–9pm during April to October and 1–6pm during November to March), and since 1992 has begun to refurbish them for this purpose. In that time, at least 46 school courtyards (roughly 50% of all school courtyards) have been turned into 'play courtyards'.

How they did it¹

- Before a play courtyard is planned in Nuremberg, all parties involved sign a joint contract. In addition to the financing, this **regulates and legitimates the process** from planning and realisation to operation and maintenance. Children in particular are closely involved in the **planning process through two user participation programmes, such that the project responds to their needs.**
- The city has long been unable to finance playgrounds on its own and has had to **adapt to increasing reliance on grants and donations**, e.g. the Sperberschule redevelopment was financed with funds from the European Commission. Funds from the federal "Socially Integrative City" programme paid for the play courtyard at the Konrad Groß School in the Nordostbahnhof housing estate. The city's "Turn 1 into 3" programme has also been in place for several years. This means that a third of the funding is provided by citizens' initiatives through donations and contributions, with the remainder coming from the city. Last but not least, a foundation of the municipal housing association (wbg) is involved, which pays grants on application by parents' initiatives.
- The secret to success lies above all in many years of effective **collaboration between several departments**, in particular the Youth Welfare Department, the Public Space Department (formerly the Horticultural Department), the Education Department and the Department for Housing and Urban Renewal. Resistance and fears from teachers, parents or neighbours, which sometimes do arise, can only be convincingly dispelled if all departments pull together and there is unrestricted political support over many decades.

Further reading

Article about the play courtyards (in German): <https://playground-landscape.com/de/article/1023-spielhoefe-schulhoefe-als-oeffentliche-spielplaetze.html>

¹ Text translated and partly adapted from original source at <https://playground-landscape.com/de/article/1023-spielhoefe-schulhoefe-als-oeffentliche-spielplaetze.html>

TOPIC: Building capacity

What it means for co-governance

Building capacity for different skills in relation to NbS is essential to achieve impacts beyond the limits of a specific project and site, and to create opportunities to empower less influential groups (recognition and procedural justice). Skills may range from know-how in designing and implementing NbS, to hands-on opportunities to help build the green space intervention, to care for plants, or to manage a green space (also see Fact sheet: Change in management responsibilities).

Key is to consider the access requirements of different target groups (e.g. municipal staff, teachers, kids, local communities etc.) in selecting formats (workshop, tour, online or offline), timing (during the school or working day, after-hours or weekend), and other barriers to participation, e.g. cost.

Recommended indicators

- #10 Different municipal departments are represented in workshops
- #13 Accessibility to workshop
- #30 Knowledge sharing: environmental education
- #32 Capacity-building of local actors
- #42 Knowledge brokers
- #64 Knowledge dissemination reach

Recommended action	Practice example
<p>Offer teachers professional development training in environmental education</p> <p>Phase: Operation</p>	<p>Name: Environmental education workshops and training provided by Department of energy and environment (DOEE)</p> <p>City: District of Columbia, Washington</p> <p>Year: ongoing</p> <p>What: DOEE offers training opportunities for teachers in internationally recognized conservation education programs like Aquatic WILD, Growing Up WILD, Project WILD, and Project Learning Tree. Workshops are free and sessions range from 3 to 8 hours. Participants learn how to provide content knowledge, critical thinking, and problem solving skills to youth to help them make prudent environmental decisions and care for natural resources.</p> <p>Participants receive classroom-ready, user-friendly instructor guides, a certificate of completion, and access to a variety of additional resources and networking opportunities with other educators.</p> <p>Link: https://doee.dc.gov/service/environmental-education-workshops-and-training</p>
<p>Offer municipal staff training in how to implement NbS.</p> <p>Phase: Operation</p>	<p>Name: Nature-based solutions training workshops for municipalities within REGREEN project</p> <p>City: Velika Gorica</p> <p>Year: 2023</p> <p>What: This workshop covered a wide range of topics: NbS projects in cities, the role of biodiversity in NbS, renaturing, green roofs, green space quality and water management. It took place over two half days and was attended by 30 participants with different areas of expertise: ministry staff, municipal staff from City of Zagreb and Velika Gorica, staff from NGOs, architects, forest managers, and urban planners. It was organised in collaboration with the Paris Region Institute. A training kit is available with recommendations on how to organise similar workshops.</p> <p>Link: Nature-based solutions training workshops in Aarhus and Velika Gorica - REGREEN (regreen-project.eu)</p>
<p>Organize educational field trips for kids</p> <p>Phase: Operation</p>	<p>Name: Dakennie educational program for pupils</p> <p>City: Rotterdam, Netherlands</p> <p>Year: 2014</p> <p>What: Dakennie is a seasonal educational program targeting pupils from primary schools and held at the DakAkker rooftop farm. It happens from September to November and from March to June. Over 2 hours, children are introduced to everything that grows on the rooftop, and learn more about urban agriculture, healthy food and biodiversity. Typically, at least two supervisors from the visiting school are present, along with three supervisors from the environmental center. Initially, the program was tested in 2014 in three schools. Reviews and feedback from kids became a base for improving program. The program is financially supported by Watersensitive Rotterdam, the municipality of Rotterdam and the Waterboard Hoogheemraadschap Schieland en de Krimpenerwaard. In 2015-2016, 1200 pupils from 39 schools took part.</p> <p>Link: https://dakakker.nl/site/?lang=en#educatie</p>

Develop guidance for residents on how to self-organise to manage a public green space.

Phase: Operation

Name: Friends of Glasgow parks – guide to organise community groups to take over the responsibility for managing public green spaces

City: Glasgow, Scotland

Year: Since 2006

What: The Municipality of Glasgow developed a detailed toolkit for citizens who want to start a community group aimed at improving open green spaces, including parks, cemeteries and woodlands. The guide includes steps to start the process, including legal aspects, the structure and responsibilities of organization; supported with examples of existed community groups. For more details, see Deeper Dive below.

Link: <https://www.glasgow.gov.uk/CHttpHandler.ashx?id=35750&p=0>

Deeper Dive: Friends of Parks Groups in Glasgow

City: Glasgow

Year: Since 2006

Figure: Friends of Glasgow Parks . Guide and information pack.
Source: Glasgow City Council Website

Friends of Glasgow Parks play a vital role in enhancing local parks and open spaces, and help local people have a greater say in how their green spaces are maintained and developed. A guide developed by the municipality helps encourage new Friends of Parks groups to form, and build their own capacity in managing open green space.

How they did it²

- A Strategic Best Value Review conducted in 2006 recommended that the city pursue partnerships with voluntary organisations to facilitate park improvements. As an answer, the City Council of Glasgow started the initiative “Friends of parks”.
- There are currently 47 such groups in the City Council’s database.
- The City provides a guide for interested citizens to follow with advice on forming a group and what steps need to be undertaken from a legal perspective. Interested citizens can contact the City Council to receive guidance from Council-appointed specialists for e.g. fund-raising and defining a manifesto, guiding principles for the organisation.
- There is no uniform expectation of the achievements of the groups besides the engagement of local citizens. Each group engages in the management and maintenance of its park as well as in planning and implementing new features of the spaces.

² Text translated and partly adapted from original source at <https://www.glasgow.gov.uk/article/19165/Friends-of-Parks-Groups>

- Some groups offer guided tours to inform the local community about the green space, its history and needs or even additional education such as the Practical Certificate in Horticulture offered by The Friends of the Glasgow Botanic Gardens.
- Challenges include keeping people engaged, finding dedicated members and the time-consuming process of funding applications.
- It is recommended that Friends of Park groups develop a short term programme of activities in line with their aims, objectives and capacity. Some activities may be one off and others may be ongoing or repeated every year, e.g. Volunteers Day, Summer Fun Event or workshop, developing a Park Management Plan etc.

Further reading

Friends of Parks guide: <https://www.glasgow.gov.uk/article/19165/Friends-of-Parks-Groups>

TOPIC: Activating the space

What it means for co-governance

Creating a new green space or redeveloping an existing one opens up **potential for new diverse uses**. However, attracting new users might take some extra effort to **'activate'** the space.

This means developing a **programme of events and activities for the space** and thinking through **potential use scenarios** throughout the year-long period. It is important to consider what kind of events would appeal to different groups, especially in the interest of reaching **under-represented or vulnerable groups**, e.g. older people, children, migrants or people with disabilities. Making events free or low cost is also important to maximise accessibility for people on lower incomes. Think too about existing events programmes, or local organisations that you might collaborate with in order to expand interest in your event, and the opportunities and limitations created by seasonal conditions. By successfully activating your space, you can open up opportunities to foster collaboration with public and private organizations, and citizens, through joint programming and/or implementing the event.

Recommended indicators

- #3 Availability: Easiness of data accessibility
- #4 Degree of participation
- #7 Strategic stakeholder cooperation
- #8 Ensuring equitable access to NbS
- #9 Accountability
- #14 Advocate representation for vulnerable groups
- #17 Valuing diversity and inclusion
- #18 Collaborative arrangements
- #20 Sense of empowerment - voice
- #26 Objectives sharedness among stakeholders
- #38 Empowering through co-creation process
- #39 Fair treatment of people across time without bias and favouritism
- #53 Attention for local conditions
- #55 Identification and involvement of diverse and vulnerable group of key actors representing different sectors
- #61 User journey participation gap
- #62 Representativeness of participants

Recommended action	Practice example
<p>EVENT CALENDAR</p> <p>Creating an online seasonal calendar of activities, detailing organization and schedules, to maintain year-round engagement with citizens.</p>	<p>Name: Event calendar for residents of Prinz-Eugen-Park neighbourhood City: Munich What: The community cooperative, established by future residents in collaboration with and supported by the City of Munich, manages local services, including event organisation. Their website hosts a monthly calendar, showcasing a diverse array of activities tailored to various resident groups. Events are categorized into Art & Culture, Sports & Health, Education, Children & Young People, Family, Seniors, Festivals, Celebrations, and Markets for easy navigation and accessibility. Link: www.prinzeugenpark.de/wann-wo-was/kalender-alle-termine.html (German)</p>
<p>GUIDED TOURS</p> <p>Opening up private spaces (e.g., gardens or courtyards) for one or several days in a year through guided visits available to the public.</p> <p>Phase: Operation</p>	<p>Name: Open Courtyards 2017 City: Lecce Year: 2017 What: For one day, citizens of Lecce received an opportunity to visit courtyards of ancient palaces that are normally inaccessible. Organised by the Association of Italian Historical Houses (ADSI) and Municipality of Lecce to raise awareness about the protection of the national architectural heritage. Link: www.data.europa.eu/data/datasets/cortili-aperti-2017?locale=en</p>
<p>COMMUNITY FESTIVALS</p> <p>Organizing a one-off or regular series of small festivals at the project site, or integrating them into an international series of events.</p> <p>Phase: Operation</p>	<p>Name: Rotterdam Rooftop Festival City: Rotterdam Year: Annual event What: On the first weekend of June, around 60 roofs are opened up for visitors, often accompanied by a guide or featuring music, theatre, or visual arts. Link: www.rotterdamsedakendagen.nl/?lang=en</p>
<p>MUSIC EVENTS</p> <p>Organizing concerts in the urban spaces.</p> <p>Phase: Operation</p>	<p>Name: Wilderness Concerts City: Hannover Year: 2016 – 2021 What: The “Cities Dare Wilderness” project is part of the overall Hanoverian program of “More Nature in the City”, a future-oriented approach to green spaces in urban areas. To actively engage the population in the caring for the wilderness, a comprehensive citizen engagement program was established. As part of this initiative, a series of “Wilderness Concerts” were organized in collaboration with the Ada-und-Theodor-Lessing-Volks-Hochschule, a public centre for adult education. Link: https://presse.hannover-stadt.de/attachments/PM7376/output_pdf_7376.pdf (German)</p>

SPORT & FITNESS

Organising free or low-cost sports & fitness classes focused on different user groups in public green spaces in cooperation with local sports clubs, associations and interested citizens e.g. yoga, dancing, etc.

Phase: Operation

Name: **Hamburg's active city festival**

City: **Hamburg**

Year: **2021**

What: **The City of Hamburg in collaboration with SPORTPLATZ GmbH and various sports associations organized a free entry festival promoting physical activity for different target groups including kids, elderly, people with disabilities.**

Link: www.activecitysummer.de

PUBLIC ART

Collaborate with local artists and/or artist-led organizations and citizens/residents to realize art projects in public open spaces.

Phase: Operation

Name: **Archiloom**

City: **Melbourne**

Year: **2019**

What:

Archiloom is an installation that was created by Slow Art Collective (an artistic collective that focuses on creative practices and ethics relating to environmental sustainability, material ethics, DIY culture and collaboration) through communal weaving workshops with various high school and primary school students at the Independent Schools Festival.

Link: www.slowartcollective.com

COMMUNITY GAMES

Installation of community game tables in project sites e.g. chess, tennis. These installations can be 'activated' by organizing competitions to further engage the community.

Phase: Operation

Name: **Outdoor chess table**

City: **London**

What: **Place for a game of chess in the University of Greenwich's Stockwell Street roof garden.**

Link: www.landscapearchitecture.org.uk/playing-chess-stockwell-street-university-greenwich-roof-garden/

Deeper dive: Active City Festival in Hamburg

City: **Hamburg**

Year: **Annual**

The City of Hamburg in collaboration with SPORTPLATZ GmbH and various sports associations organized a free entry festival promoting physical activity for different target groups including kids, elderly, people with disabilities.

How they did it³

- The Annual Active City Festival, is a key component of Hamburg Senate's Active City Strategy, aimed at promoting a vibrant and healthy urban lifestyle where sports and exercise are accessible to all.
- Organized by SPORTPLATZ GmbH in collaboration with the city and local clubs since 2018, the festival champions public sports spaces and inclusivity.
- The festival is held annually for one day, from 12:00 p.m. to 6:00 p.m
- Entry is free, making it inclusive for people on lower incomes.
- During its first year, it attracted over 8,000 visitors and collaborated with more than 20 sports clubs.
- The festival caters to various physical abilities and age groups, fostering inclusivity. It offers 23 different types of sports, including:
- „Walking Football” – a variant of football that is aimed at keeping people aged over 50 involved with football if, due to a lack of mobility or for other reasons, they are not able to play the traditional game; FUNini – soccer for children; Inclusive boccia – is a ball game that includes players with cerebral palsy and any other disabilities that affect motor skills; as well as boules and Viking chess to fencing, futsal, rowing, stand-up paddling, and leisure golf.

Further reading

City of Hamburg's event page: www.activecitysummer.de

For more on incentives to attract people to events, see the presentation 'Can we pay people to participate? [Incentives for workshop attendees](#)' (11 July 2023)

For guidance on running a gender-sensitive event, see the JUSTNature gender guidelines 'Checklist for gender sensitive workshop facilitation'.

³ Text translated and partly adapted from original source at www.activecitysummer.de

TOPIC: Change in management responsibilities

What it means for co-governance	Recommended indicators
<p>Practices that delegate management responsibilities to citizens are widely seen as yielding positive effects for nature conservation and biodiversity protection. This can also alleviate the burden on city administrations in terms of resources, especially in cases of limited municipal capacity.</p>	<p>#3 Availability: Easiness of data accessibility #4 Degree of participation #7 Strategic stakeholder cooperation #8 Ensuring equitable access to NbS #9 Accountability</p>
<p>By empowering residents to manage the public spaces in their neighbourhoods, the city can draw on residents' local knowledge to more directly address local needs, thus improving recognitional and procedural justice. It can also result in increased trust in the city administration, better communication between city officials and the community members, and increased sense of place attachment and ownership among community members.</p>	<p>#14 Advocate representation for vulnerable groups #17 Valuing diversity and inclusion #18 Collaborative arrangements #20 Sense of empowerment - voice #26 Objectives sharedness among stakeholders</p>
<p>Providing opportunities to gain new skills and experience can also be an extra incentive for community members to take on a new role (also see Fact sheet: Building Capacity).</p>	<p>#38 Empowering through co-creation process #39 Fair treatment of people across time without bias and favouritism #42 Knowledge brokers #43 Linking environmental understanding with values of local actors #50 Process-oriented approach #53 Attention for local conditions #55 Identification and involvement of diverse and vulnerable group of key actors representing different sectors #61 User journey participation gap #62 Representativeness of participants</p>

Recommended action	Practice example
<p>Establish a new management team or volunteer group to effectively coordinate activities on the site (e.g. gardening activities, community participatory programs etc.)</p> <p>Phase: Operation</p>	<p>Name: GeQo eG cooperative for neighbourhood organisation</p> <p>City: Munich</p> <p>Year: Since 2018</p> <p>What: The GeQo cooperative, formed by Prinz Eugen neighbourhood residents in 2018, responsible for local services such as mobility, community spaces, and events for citizens. Established in partnership with and supported financially by the City of Munich. For more details, see Deeper Dive below.</p> <p>Link: www.prinzeugenpark.de</p>
<p>Establish a private organisation (knowledge broker) that is responsible for supporting local citizens to be involved in NBS management.</p> <p>Phase: Operation</p>	<p>Name: GB Stern</p> <p>City: Vienna</p> <p>Year: Since 2021</p> <p>What: GB Stern, founded in the 1970s in a local pub, is a private company that provides free advice on living environments, infrastructure, and urban renewal. One of their key roles is supporting citizens to participate in the creation and management of urban green spaces, from small street tree pits to neighbourhood gardens. They facilitate learning processes and offer ongoing support to participants.</p> <p>The company is commissioned by the City of Vienna through an EU-wide tendering procedure, with contracts typically running for 3-6 years.</p> <p>Link: www.gbstern.at/themen-projekte/urbanes-garteln/baumscheibengarteln-in-wien/garteln-in-floridsdorf/ (German)</p>

Deeper dive: GeQo Cooperative for neighbourhood organization

City: **Munich**

Year: **2018**

The GeQo cooperative, originally comprised of future residents of the planned new Prinz Eugen Park neighbourhood, was established during the planning phase to manage local services, including mobility, community spaces, and events. The cooperative's motto, "from the neighbourhood for the neighbourhood," reflects its commitment to community-driven initiatives and empowerment. The cooperative engages residents in community activities, supports the city in disseminating information, manages common areas and operates a neighbourhood headquarters with café, mobility point and concierge point. The model is so far unique in Germany.

How they did it⁴

- The City of Munich has subsidized and collaborated with this cooperative since it began.
- At the beginning, residents were involved on a voluntary basis, and organised in different working groups. After the neighbourhood was completed, some residents expressed a desire to independently manage neighbourhood activities, instead of outsourcing them to a private entity.
- The residents proposed creating a Nachbarschaftstreff (neighbourhood meeting point) for this purpose, which would usually be a process led by the city administration through a tender for services. In this case, the City decided to engage the residents directly, without a tender process.
- Since 2019, a small number of residents are paid by the City to manage the cooperative. The legal form of cooperation was a result of joint discussion between residents and city representatives about the possible structural model of cooperative.
- The City of Munich's Social Department subsidized the pilot model under the "neighborhood-based residents' work" initiative ([Quartiersbezogenen Bewohnerarbeit](#)), aimed at fostering community engagement through provision of community meeting spaces.
- In relation to green space, the GeQo cooperative collaborates closely with the horticulture department, assisting in disseminating information about public green spaces and community events through newsletters and utilizing the centrally-located community center.

Further reading

See the cooperative website at www.prinzeugenpark.de

⁴ The information above was obtained during an interview with a representative of GeQo eG, in August 2023.